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DEVELOPING A PRIVACY POLICY

PREFACE

There is some risk of disclosing identities of individuals (or entities) and their sensitive data that exists in every data file that is released. A privacy policy should describe a process that considers whether the release of the data file followed reasonable procedures and a process that applies appropriate data use restrictions and access controls. At the very least, the risk of re-identification should be minimized after considering the possible approaches to re-identify persons using existing technology and public or commercially available information. Furthermore, it is important to be aware that the privacy of individuals can be impacted by a data release whether or not the person is in the file.

BACKGROUND

The legal framework for privacy policies is based on various federal and state statutes and case law. The majority of these laws focus on protecting the identifiability of persons as the basis and approach for protecting privacy interests. Privacy interests are fragmented across various subject matter topics and privacy protections and remedies also vary across subject matter. The current requirements to protect privacy interests places a strong emphasis on whether personally identifiable information (PII) exists in the data file as a determining factor on whether privacy protections should apply. The definition of PII is so broad that it refers to any piece of information that can be used on its own or with other information to re-identify, contact, or locate a person in a file. The reliance on a vague term such as PII for whether a data system requires privacy protection provides no guidance for developing a privacy policy in the digital age. The reliance on the presence or absence of PII in a data file should not be determinative on whether privacy protections apply.

RECOMMENDATION

The current privacy legal framework needs to change and focus on applying appropriate data use restrictions, assessing the risk of re-identification, creating the process for developing the data set, and determining the contents of a data set. A privacy policy should focus on ensuring that the process and procedural actions to protect information are followed. New statutes need to be drafted that require privacy protections regardless if PII exists in a file and impose penalties without requiring persons to show harm or damages. The new legal framework needs to focus on data use restrictions and access controls as the main approach for protecting privacy interests throughout the life cycle of information beginning with data collection and ending with record destruction.

GUIDANCE

Privacy interests should apply regardless of whether persons are identifiable in a file and regardless of whether PII exists. The existence of PII in a data file is only one factor as a high

risk variable in determining the identifiability of the data. For example, combinations of indirect identifying variables can lead to the identity of an individual, or the full or partial data vector for a record may be linkable to another file containing PII. A privacy policy should associate the levels of access and the level of data protection methods (data protection methodology) to minimize re-identification risk. For example, a data set in a physical enclave with strong access controls may be able to allow access to more raw data than a publicly accessible dataset. Strong privacy protections rely on applying appropriate data protection methods, data use restrictions and access controls. Privacy rights should be enforceable without the need to show direct or indirect damages. Privacy violations should be noted when the process that is described in a privacy policy is violated, the required actions are not applied, or the actions taken do not comply with the process.

Essential elements for a data privacy policy should, at the very least, include:

1. Describe allowable uses of the data. Some uses are more problematic and require more controls or restrictions. Determine whether researcher access to microdata will be allowed. Use specific informed consent statements and avoid the use of broad consent forms.
2. Describe the source(s) of the data, and to measure re-identification risk, review the sample size and whether sample weights are used in the design, the population size, whether high risk variables exist in the data file that can be matched to external files, and whether multiple records in a data file are known to belong to the same cluster. Longitudinal and panel surveys create a special case of disclosure risk that may be associated with linked files. In this case, the disclosure risk of a microdata file increases if some records on the file are released on another file with more detailed or overlapping recodes (categorizations) of the same variables.
3. Describe the key re-identification risk elements and potential attack scenarios that the policy is designed to protect against.
4. Determine what data protection methods should be applied to data releases that are commensurate with the proposed use(s).
5. Describe the data access controls for the data system. Reference whether any privacy protection certificates/certificates of confidentiality apply that reduce the risk of required disclosures of identifiable information.
6. Verify the organization has the resources, expertise, and capability to provide appropriate guarantees, assurances, or attestations for privacy protection when information is being collected.
7. Avoid broad consent statements and develop specific consent and use statements for the information that is collected.
8. State whether information will be disclosed to the third parties for other purposes such as research and/or marketing.
9. Describe the baseline anonymization process and determine the threshold level for re-identification of data subjects in the file to be publicly released. Consider how to minimize what information is collected and stored to reduce the probability of linking records to re-identify individuals.
10. New privacy statutes should provide clear enforcement sanctions via civil damages and criminal penalties for violating the requirements and procedures stated in the policy without the requirement for a person to show harm or damages.

The important steps to follow for implementing a privacy policy include: assess the data to be released and the risks of disclosing identifiable information; minimize the data to be released without compromising utility; apply reasonable data protection methods, develop and apply appropriate monitoring; accountability and breach response plan (i.e., use checklist or process approach similar to the approach used for developing a Privacy Impact Assessment).

DATA RELEASE POLICIES

A data release policy should be consistent with and support the privacy policy.

Factors to consider when drafting a data release policy.

1. Different approaches for assessing re-identification risk.
2. Different assumptions for determining the sophistication of the data intruder.
 - a. The likelihood the intruder would attempt to re-identify. The likelihood is often unknown so assumptions need to be stated regarding the sophistication and competency of statistical and computational skills needed for re-identification. Apply a reasonableness standard in terms of technology, software, and auxiliary data files that the data supplier is aware of after making a good faith effort to identify other linkable data files. Auxiliary files that may not appear useful for linking records may have greater value in the future depending on the growth of available data sources. This requires an annual review to evaluate risk and to account for an increase in available data files within a global network, and the development of new statistical skills and methods.
 - b. The amount of effort an intruder would spend trying to re-identify. There may be facts or circumstances that the data supplier is aware of that may change these assumptions and require greater protection such as the likelihood of linkable auxiliary data that can be used for re-identification, or the intruder being a foreign government or other entity with significant resources available.
3. Different types of harms that can arise from an unauthorized disclosure.
4. Differences in the resource capability, expertise, and effort an organization can spend for applying and testing data protection methods.
5. Differences in the utility of the de-identified data. In evaluating the utility of the data, the needs of researcher access to the actual data versus using synthetic data should be considered.

The process for releasing data should include:

1. An enforceable commitment not to re-identify.
2. An audit trail on access to data.
3. A measure of re-identification risk before and after data protections are applied.
4. Application of data protection methods to block reasonable efforts to re-identify persons.
5. An anonymization process that applies to all data and follows a “reasonableness” standard.
6. Other access and disclosure controls, such as federal privacy certificates, data licensing terms, or memorandum of understandings for enforceable control of data releases.

No single risk policy is appropriate for all types of data releases. The minimum risk tolerance should be established on the probability of re-identification of a person in a data file. More broadly, the risk ought to be the disclosure risk of an individual or the sensitive characteristics regardless if a person is in the database or not.